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SELECTION OF SURFACE EXPLOITATION SYSTEMS IN THE KOSOVO LIGNITE BASIN (SIBOVČ FIELD)

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Abstract

This paper presents the selection of coal exploitation methods in the Kosovo basin, from the initial phases of development to the present day. The experience gained from the exploitation of earlier mines has contributed to the planning of the new lignite mine in the Sibovč field. Within this basin, there are three potential fields for lignite exploitation, but the Sibovč field—due to its geological, technical, and economic characteristics—is considered a strategic priority for development. The field contains over 990 million tons of lignite reserves, sufficient for more than 40 years of operation. Detailed studies have confirmed that the Sibovč field can provide an annual production capacity of up to 20 million tons of lignite. To meet the demands of existing and future power plants, ensure a stable supply for domestic consumers, and address export needs, Kosovo must increase its lignite production capacity to 15 million tons per year starting from 2028. The field has the potential to supply a power plant with an installed capacity of 2000–2500 MW.

Keywords: surface exploitation, lignite, reserves, Kosovo basin, Sibovč field

Introduction

This coal-bearing basin represents the largest open-pit mines in the Republic of Kosovo (Figure 1). Mining operations for underground lignite exploitation in the Kosovo basin were carried out from 1922 to 1966 (6,401,434 t), and at the "Krushevc" location from 1948 to 1966 (3,000,000 t) and at "Sibovč" from 1952 to 1958 (255,000 t).

The first works for the opening of the surface mine in the Kosovo coal basin began at the end of 1956, in Mirash, while coal production began in 1958. In the first phase of the mine opening, machinery with interrupted operation was used (discontinuous exploitation system) and shovel and dragline excavators with a bucket volume of 4m³ were used for the excavation of the cover and the extraction of lignite.

The transportation of the barren material was done with wagons with a volume of 25m³, while the coal was transported with wagons with a sloping bottom and a volume of 50m³, which were pulled by electric locomotives of the LE-3 type with a carrying capacity of 70t. With this type of equipment and for a discovery coefficient of 1.0 m³/t, in 1963 a capacity of 3000 t/day was achieved. Since 1964, belt conveyors with a width of 1000 mm have been installed in this mine at the lignite exploitation stages and 1200 mm at the overburden exploitation stages, while the excavation of lignite and overburden was carried out with a rotor excavator of the type SRs470.15/3.5 with a theoretical capacity of 1960 m³/h, which, in order to excavate the overburden consisting of hard marls and compact lignite, were constructed with 400 kW impeller motors. For stacking of barren formations, stackers of the type AR_s-B 2500.50 with a theoretical capacity of 2500 m³/h were used. The exploitation with the reconstruction of the career carried out in 1966 has reached a capacity of approximately 10000 t/day.

The surface mine in the Kosovo Basin was opened in 1964 in Bardh, applying the discontinuous exploitation system (with shovel excavators and railway transport borrowed from the Mirash mine), and in 1967 the equipment for the normal technological process in the discovery was installed (Figure. 2). Lignite extraction in the Bardh mine began at a rate of about 12,000 t/day. For the extraction of lignite in this phase of development, excavators with rotors of the SRs 470.15/3.5 type were used, while for the removal of the cover, excavators with rotors of the SRs 470.20/3 type with motors installed in the working wheel with a power of 250kW were used. The transportation of lignite and overburden clay formations was carried out with 1200 mm wide conveyor belts at the mining stages, while those with a belt width of 1400 mm were applied to the collecting conveyors to the stacks.

The barren formations, which were excavated by two excavators, were stacked by a stacker of the type AR_s-B 2500.50 and AR_s-B 3000.50, respectively. The new type of excavator with rotor SRs 470.20/3 with increased gripping height and with a motor with lower power of the working wheel, was not adapted to the working conditions in hard marl clay, so in 1974 the new type of excavator with rotor SRs 470.17/6 with reduced digging height and increased power of the working wheel motor of 320kW was put into operation. After the successful work of this excavator, the investor approached the reconstruction from 20 m to 17m, and the installation of working wheel motors with increased power was made. This construction comes at a time when the reconstruction of the Bardhi quarry has foreseen an increase in the production capacity of lignite with new and reconstructed working equipment.

In the excavation of the cover, it was planned to apply the excavator type SRs 1300.26/6+VR with a theoretical capacity of 4200 m³/h with a motor power of the working wheel of 630kW, which was planned to

work in a system with 1600 mm wide conveyor belts and stackers of the type A₂R_s-B4400,60 with a theoretical capacity of 4400m³/h. In the extraction of lignite, it was planned to use the rotor excavator from the front stages of the type SRs 470.15/3.5 and the reconstructed type of the excavator SRs 470.17/16, as well as the dragline excavator of the type ESH 5/45 for the excavation of the ceiling parts of the lignite layers with variable thickness. In the Bardhi mine, in 1979, the first excavator of the SRs-1300.26/2+VR type was put into operation with a production capacity of about 300,000 t/day [1-4].

Since 1964, conveyor belts with a width of 1000 mm have been installed in this quarry at the coal exploitation levels and 1200 mm at the overburden exploitation levels, while the coal and overburden excavation was carried out with a rotor excavator of the type SRs 470.15/3.5 with a theoretical capacity of 1960 m³/h, which, in order to excavate the overburden composed of hard marl and compact lignite, are better equipped with engines with a working wheel of 400

Figure 1. The Kosovo Coal Basin

In the excavation of the cover, it was planned to use the excavator type SRs-1300.26/6+VR with a theoretical capacity of 3500 m³/h and a motor power of the working wheel of 630 kW, which was planned to work in a system with 1600mm wide conveyor belts and stackers of the A₂R_s-B4400,60 type with a theoretical capacity of 4400 m³/h. In the extraction of coal, it was planned to use the rotor excavator from the front stages of the SRs-470.15/3,5 type and the reconstructed type of the SRs-470,17/16 excavator, as well as the dragline excavator of the ESH -5/45 type for the excavation of the ceiling parts of the lignite layers of variable thickness.

The first excavator of the SRs1300,26/2+VR type was put into operation in 1979, so that the Bardhi mine, according to the projected production dynamics, should

kW. For the stacking of barren formations, stackers of the type AR_s-B 2500.50 with a theoretical capacity of 2500 m³/h were used. The exploitation with the reconstruction of the quarry carried out in 1966 has reached a capacity of approximately 10,000 t/day.

The second surface mine in the Kosovo is basin in Bardh was opened in 1964 with a discontinuous exploitation system (with shovel excavators and wagon transportation) borrowed from the Mirash quarry, and in 1967 the equipment for the normal technological process in the discovery was installed. The productivity (extraction) of coal in the Bardh career started at about 12,000 t/day. For the extraction of coal in this phase of development, excavators of the SRs470.15/3.5 type were used, while for the displacement of the cover, excavators of the SRs470.20/3 type with 250 kW impeller motors were used. The transportation of coal and cover material was carried out with conveyor belts with a width of 1200 mm in the exploitation steps, and 1400 mm in the collecting conveyors to the stacks.

Figure 2. Map of potential and exploited fields in the Kosovo Lignite Basin

have achieved a daily production of approximately 30,000 t/day by 1985. In parallel with the achievement of the projected capacity in the Bardhi mine by 1985, the opening of the Sibovc mine was foreseen, which together with the foreseen equipment represents the next stage of development in this lignite base and that is: – for the excavation of the cover and coal, rotor excavators with a theoretical capacity of 4,500 m³/day with an excavation height of up to 28 m were foreseen, which, taking into account the alternating work in the cover and in the coal, would achieve an average productivity of approximately 2,500 [(m³·m·x·f/day)].

- for the transportation of the cover and coal, it was planned to use conveyor belts with a width of 1800 mm,

while for the stacking of the waste, stackers with a theoretical capacity of 5500 m³/h with a 100m long stacking console were planned.

To achieve the final capacity, it was planned to need six exploitation systems, three in discovery and three in extraction, and taking into account the very favorable discovery coefficient of 0.88 m³/t, an average daily capacity of approximately 50,000 t/day (lignite) is ensured, which, taking into account the very favorable exploitation conditions for entering the individual systems, can be achieved in the 10th year from the opening. In the Sibovc South West career, exploitation has been completed in 2024 and the opening of new careers (surface mine), is foreseen in the direction of Hada, Shipitulla and Lajthishta, taking into account the large exploitable reserves of lignite in the Kosovo coal basin [4,5].

Very favorable conditions for the opening of large careers with a capacity of over 100,000t of lignite per day, using the practice of several decades of extraction in the Kosovo coal basin. It is estimated that excavators

will be successfully used (in technical and economic terms), whose theoretical capacity will reach approximately 10,000 m³/h in the discovery and extraction of lignite can provide a capacity of 50,000 [(m³×m×f)/day)]. Excavators with larger capacity, due to limited heights of steps in the cover and difficult maintenance, would likely exceed the upper limit of economics and in the future will represent an optimal solution for lignite exploitation in the Kosovo basin.

Three units of TC “Kosova” A” and two units of TC “Kosova” B” provide an hourly capacity of 845-910 MW. So far, the existing Sibovc South-West mine has supplied the Kosovo A and Kosovo B power plants, in which mining activities are on the verge of extinction due to the depletion of lignite reserves (Figure 3). Therefore, in order to meet the requirements of these power plants with lignite and supply other domestic consumers and export requirements, Kosovo should increase its lignite production capacity by 2028 to 15 million per year.

Figure 3. View of the Sibovci South-West open-pit lignite mine

The current status and general overview of the exploited mines and potential fields for opening and exploitation included in the Central Zone of the Kosovo Basin are presented in Figure 4. The potential fields for future exploitation are: Sibovci Field, Field D and Field South, only the Sibovci mining field has been explored in detail and it has been found that it can provide annual lignite production of up to 20 million tons/year.

The exploitation of lignite in the Sibovci field, which possesses lignite reserves of category A, offers the best opportunity for supplying lignite to existing

and possibly new thermal power plants [6-8]. Field D is promising but has not been explored sufficiently for immediate opening. This field is characterized by a small cover thickness and a favorable discovery coefficient, but creates unfavorable conditions for the environment due to ash stacking. The exploitation of Field South would have higher costs due to the unfavorable discovery coefficient and as a result of external stacking [9]. Table 1. gives the characteristics of the three potential fields.

Figure. 4 Overview of potential fields for lignite exploitation (KEK)

Table 1.

Characteristics of potential lignite fields in the Kosovo Basin

Criteria	Sibovc Field	Field South	Field D
Coal reserves (mt) - Geological	990	537	395
Coal reserves (mt) - Exploitable	830	370	280
Supply capacity per power plant (MW)	2000	1000	600
Cover-Coal Ratio (m ³ /t)	0.85:1	2.8:1	0.9:1
LHV (kJ/kg)	8300	8000-8300	7300
Area (km ²)	19.7	8.0	7.8
Period of use (years)	>40	40	40

Material and methods

For the realization of this work, data and information from the technical documentation compiled by the Directorate of Planning and Analysis of Production Development within KEK Sh. A - Lignite Production Unit were used.

In addition, statistical data generated from topographic and geological measurements in the field, as well as data on the geographical position and geological configuration of the lignite layers and the cover, were analyzed. In this context, the general geological structure of the Kosovo Lignite Field was taken into consideration, with special emphasis on the Sibovc Mining Field. The Sibovc Mining Field lies in the northern part of the exploited Mirash and Bardh mines near the Kosovo "B" thermal power plant (Figure 2). The area of the field covers about 19.7 km² with a maximum usable width (east-west extension) of 3.8 km and a length of about 6 km [9]. Coal mining in this field offers the best opportunity to supply coal to a new thermal power plant. The field can provide coal for a thermal power plant with a capacity of 2000 – 2500 MW. The Sibovc Mining Field includes the villages of Hade, Sibovc, Lajthishta and a part of the village of Shipitull which, for the most part, is outside the scope of exploitation (Figure 2). In general, the deposit is characterized by a lignite layer with a thickness of at least 10 to 100 m, which is covered by a sterile layer with a thickness of 20 to 150 m [10]. Lignite extracted from the open-pit mine in this deposit is expected to be used to supply raw materials to the existing Kosovo A and Kosovo B thermal power plants and other consumers inside and outside the country.

The application of the lignite exploitation system with surface mining operations is made suitable by the typical features of the Sibovc Field (Kosovo Basin),

such as: the relatively large and almost horizontal thickness of the lignite layer and the large and fairly uniform spatial extension, the low discovery coefficient, the relatively small cover thickness or mine depth, the properties of the ceiling and floor formations [11]. Surface exploitation represents the most widespread system of exploitation of useful minerals anywhere in the world. In the USA, surface exploitation accounts for about 85% of all exploitation of useful minerals (excluding oil and natural gas). Thus, it can be stated that in the USA almost all metallic minerals (98%) and non-metallic minerals (97%) as well as 61% of coal are extracted using surface exploitation [12]. Therefore, surface exploitation is the predominant method of extracting useful solid minerals worldwide, including Kosovo (75%).

The superficial exploitation of lignite represents a technological process that takes place in two steps:

Step 1: Exploration mining works for removing the cover, and

Step 2: Mining works for extracting lignite, i.e. for exploiting the resource.

The basic steps in the selection methodology are presented in Figure. 5 and are listed as follows.

The construction of a surface mine is carried out in several stages, consisting of a planned scheme or a set of alternative schemes, followed by the evaluation and selection of the optimal scheme (Figure 6). The final economic construction of a surface mine depends on factors that the mining engineer cannot control, such as:

- the geometric contours of the mineral body,
- the distribution of the mineral within the mineral body,
- the topography,
- the maximum allowable angles of slope inclination, etc.

However, the economic evaluation of the exploitation program is related to factors determined by the mining engineer, such as the selection of the exploitation coefficient, production rates, and equipment [12]. The construction of a surface mine is an extremely

complex task, the solution of which requires taking into account a whole series of natural and technical-economic factors. Natural factors represent two basic groups that constitute a set of qualitative and quantitative data such as:

Figure 5. Basic steps of the exploitation system selection methodology

The ratio of natural and techno-economic factors during the formation of mines with surface exploitation is determined by certain laws. Compared with underground exploitation systems, surface exploitation systems require the removal of a large amount of overburden and its transportation outside the mine contours. The cost of obtaining useful ore from surface mining constitutes the largest part of the total cost of technological operations in surface mining, because access to the mineral body is very fast and takes less time compared to underground exploitation of minerals [12]. Thus, the extraction of ore from under the cover can begin only with some time delay from the beginning of the removal of overburden. Also, surface exploitation has practically unlimited possibilities of using high-

performance mining and transport equipment, which can provide the highest technical and economic parameters. It is worth noting that surface mining is distinguished by 3-5 times higher productivity than underground mining systems, lower cost per unit of production, safer and more hygienic working conditions, more complete extraction of the mineral, but is considered an extraction method with excellent performance that manages to remove 110-150 million tons of rock per year and at a depth of 500m. However, capital investments in surface mines are large and reach hundreds of millions of dollars or even more, which imposes that decisions on the construction of new surface mines or the reconstruction of existing ones must be justified in economic terms.

Figure 6. Schematic representation of the mine construction process (according to Fourie, 1992)

Results and Discussion

The results of the analysis of the technical, economic and environmental characteristics of three potential lignite fields in the Kosovo Basin – Sibovc Field, Field South and Field D – show that Sibovc Field represents the most favorable alternative for the sustainable supply of existing and potentially new thermal power plants.

Sibovc Field has the largest geological (990 million tons) and exploitable (830 million tons) reserves, with a mining life of over 40 years. With a coal-to-cover ratio of only 0.85:1 and a LHV (Lower Heating Value) value of 8300 kJ/kg, this field represents the best balance between economic efficiency and energy potential. The area of 19.7 km² also makes it suitable for large-scale operations.

Field D, although promising due to its favorable overburden-to-coal ratio (0.9:1) and small overburden thickness, is currently not ready for exploitation due to the lack of sufficient exploration. Furthermore, it presents environmental challenges due to the need for ash stockpiling, raising concerns about environmental impacts and post-exploitation rehabilitation costs.

The Southern Field, although explored, presents economic disadvantages due to its high discovery ratio (2.8:1), resulting in high exploitation costs. The LHV value ranges between 8000–8300 kJ/kg, but the external stockpiling and the smaller surface area (8.0 km²) constitute other factors that negatively affect the profitability of this field for long-term exploitation.

In conclusion, the analysis shows that priority should be given to the exploitation of the Sibovc Field, due to the more favorable geological, technical and economic conditions. However, to ensure the diversification and long-term sustainability of lignite supply, it is recommended to intensify research in Field D and develop measures to minimize environmental impacts in all areas.

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References:

1. Përgatitja e planit të detajuar të prodhimit dhe investimeve për minierën e re në KEK. Prishtinë, (Technical Planning, KEK, 2019).
2. Hyseni A, Haliti R, (2025). Enhancing the efficiency of lignite exploitation in the Kosovo mining field. Proceedings 16th Conferences with Internacional participation, Ljubljana, pp. 27
3. Ahmeti H, Duraku V, (2023). Formation of the Geometry of the Side Slopes from the Geotechnical Aspect for the Recultivation of the Degraded Area from Coal Mining. *Journal of Ecological Engineering* 24(1),195–204. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/156001>
4. Mirena A, (2022). Coal reserves and quality of Sibovc for long -term supply needs in the corporation energy of Kosovo. Master Thesis. Faculty of Geosciences University “Isa Boletini” Mitrovicë.
5. Mirena A, (2019). Deep geological drilling research in southwest Sibovc (Inkos Sh.A. Institute-Obiliq). Prishtine.
6. Arifi B, Spath Ph, (2018). Sleeping on coal: Trajectories of promoting and opposing a lignite-fired power plant in Kosovo. *Energy Research & Social Science* 41,118–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.04.012>.
7. Ahmeti H, Duraku V, (2018). Endangering Residents in Shipitull Village by Landslide at the Surface Mining in South West Sibovc. *Journal of Civil & Environmental Engineering* 8 (ISSN: 2165-784X), 1-8. DOI: 10.4172/2165-784X.1000315.
8. Hyseni A, Muzaqi E, (2021). Sulphur content at the coal deposit in Sibovc. *International Multidisciplinary Geosciences Conference IMG2021, Mitrovicë.*
9. Ymeri A, (2015). Geological-sedimentological assessment and petrographic features of the Kosovo coal basin. Albanian PhD Thesis. Faculty of Geosciences and Mining University Tiranë.
10. Cehlar M, Rybar R, Pinka J, Haxhiu L, Beer M, (2013). Analysis of suitability for development of new mining field in north part of Kosovo lignite basin-Sibovc. *Arch. Min. Sci.*, 58(2), 557–568. DOI:10.2478/amsc-2013-0038.
11. Haliti R, (2024). Statistika në inxhinierin minierare: Prishtinë, pp. 205
12. Bytyqi A, Goskoli E, (2012). Opportunities and Prospects of Coal exploitation in the area of Sibovc. Universitas Publishing House Petroșani–România, 2012 13, 20.